

UDK 904

**THE ROLE OF NAVRUZ AHMADKHAN OF THE HISTORY
OF UZBEK STATEHOOD**

Mirzaev B.N

Doctor of philosophy (PhD) in historical sciences, teacher
Jizzakh state pedagogical university

Annotation: This article represents the political and social activities of Navruz Ahmad Khan, known as Barakkhan, a skilled politician and statesman who sought to alleviate the unstable situation in the Movarounnahr region in the mid-16th century, based on historical written sources.

Keywords: Barakkhan, Movarounnahr, Miyankol, Safavids, madrasah, weir.

В статье рассматривается политическая и общественная деятельность Навруза Ахмад-хана, известного как Баракхан, опытного политика и государственного деятеля, который стремился облегчить нестабильную ситуацию в регионе Мавераннахра в середине 16 века, основываясь на исторических письменных источниках.

Ключевые слова: Баракхан, Мавераннахр, Маянкол, сефевиды, медресе, плотина.

The assessment of the past must be objective and free from various ideological views. The establishment of the channel "History of Uzbekistan" by the National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan plays as a huge source to upbringing young people to feel sense of national pride towards the invaluable heritage of our great

scholars and writers, scientists and the courage of our invincible commanders and figures. [1, p. 3]

It is known that by the 40s of the 16th century, the struggle between the great nobles and dynasties for the capital cities and estates of Movarounnahr had intensified again. Among the representatives of the ruling family, the struggle intensified, especially for Bukhara and Samarkand. During this period, Samarkand was ruled by Abdullatifkhan (1541-1552) who was the third son of Kuchkunchikhan and Bukhara was ruled by Ubaydullakhan's son Abdulazizkhan (1540-1550), both of those rulers considered themselves as official khans [2,307].

It should be noted that in the work "Abdullanoma" by Hafiz Tanish al-Bukhari, "... After the death of Abdulaziz Khan, the reins of the Bukhara government was ruled by Muhammadyar Sultan ibn Suyunchmuhammad Sultan ibn Shahid Hakan Abulgazi Muhammad Shaibanikhan. Faridun, the mighty king Abulfath Pirmuhammadkhan, visited Bukhara province from Balkh in order to express condolence and conquered the country of (Muhammadyar sultan) at that time"[3,94]. In the period of ongoing dynastic struggles, Navruz Ahmadkhan who was the grandson of Mirzo Ulugbek's daughter Robiya Sultan and the second son of Shaybani Suyunchkhojakhan, also known as Barakkhan, entered the political arena.

In other words, the historical book "Abdullanoma" mentions about, ".. As soon as this event took place, Abdullatifkhan, the son of the Emigrant Sultan, from Samarkand and Navruz Ahmadkhan, the son of Suyunchkhojakhan set out with a large army to conquer Bukhara and Miyankol from Turkestan and Tashkent in 1550" [3,94]. The information about Barakkhan was written partially in the sources, mainly about his army, his reign and sometimes small events in the country. In particular, it was mentioned in Muhammadyar ibn Arab Katagan's Musahhir al-Bilad: "He was the brave heart sultan. After the death of his brother Keldi Muhammad sultan, he ruled the government in Tashkent.

According to the facts, the poet Vasifi was engaged in the upbringing of Barakkhan. In this sense, Barakkhan learned poetry, music, singing, weight and verse

from Wasifi during his childhood. Barakkhan was more involved in horseback riding and military training as well. Barakkhan organized many military campaigns to expand his country. As a result of these campaigns, in 1551 (Hijri 961) Navruz Ahmad Khan conquered Samarkand and became the supreme ruler of the Shaybanids. He was declared as the chief Uzbek khan in the written sources.

In particular, in Muhammadyar ibn Arab Katagan's *Musahhir al-Bilad*, "...Alexander the Great Sultan (Abdullah II) was forced to retreat and returned to

Nasaf. Sultan Sa'id visited the high-ranking Sheikh Muhammad Sadik who was a descendant of Sheikh Abulhasan Ishqi, and Navruz Ahmadkhan received with honor with the help of the sheikh's relatives. Navruz Ahmadkhan encouraged and promised him to liberate Bukhara from the hands of Burhan Sultan and make him a sultan of Bukhara in exchange for Samarkand"[4,241]. It is clear that Navruz Ahmadkhan, put an end partially to internal disintegration in the state. During his reign, Navruz Ahmadkhan, followed the interests of the population, organized the irrigation of new fields and tried to implement economic reforms in the country. In particular, his emphasis on the irrigation system was mentioned in the sources. In particular, Hasanbek Rumlu's *Ahsan ut-tavorix* ("Palace of History") (1572-77) states that "he decided to build a canal from the Shohruhiya River (Syrdarya) to Samarkand and to place twenty thousand of his people around it" [5]. According to Muhammadyar ibn Arab Katagan, "six years after the khanate's independence, he died on September 24, 1556 (Hij. 963) in the Khoja rabot district of Samarkand, at the beginning of the Kuhak River" [4,168]. Some sources indicate the reason for being in this area was that Barakkhan came to repair the main structure of the Dargom canal which started from the Zarafshan River - Ravotkhoja dam and died suddenly here. He was buried in Samarkand in 1556.

In general, based on the information in the written sources about the identity of Navruz Ahmadkhan (Barakkhan), we make the following conclusions:

1. Navruz Ahmad Khan is a historical figure who was able to put an end to the internal divisions in Movarounnahr in a short period of time as a commander and a skilful politician.

2. Navruz Ahmadkhan had respected priests highly among the Shaybani sultans, such as Muhammad Shaybanikhan and Abulgazi Ubaydulla Bahodirkhan.

3. The fact that Navruz Ahmadkhan was mentioned in written sources as a creative and reformist ruler and a patriot person.

During the years of independence, we must strengthen the spiritual and enlightenment foundations of society in our country, realize our national identity, study the ancient and rich history of our country and support research activities of the scientists in the field of humanities sciences.

References:

1. “The pace of our development path will increase” - The Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on December 28, 2018. // People’s word newspaper. December 28, 2018.

2. Eshov B. History of state and local government in Uzbekistan. Tashkent, “Yangi asr avlodi” publishing house, 2012. -p.556

3. Hafiz Tanish Bukhari. Abdullanoma. Book 1. Tashkent, “Sharq” publishing house, 1999. - p.416

4. Muhammadyar ibn Arab Katagan. Musaxxir al-bilod. Tashkent, “Yangi asr avlodi” publishing house, 2009 - p.432

5. <https://shosh.uz/Tashkentliklar-Baroqhon-Navroz-Ahmadhon>